

MECHANISMS AND ADVANTAGE OF TEACHING STUDENTS TO CREATIVE THINKING THROUGH MEDIA EDUCATION METHODS IN THE INFORMATIONAL EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

We live in such a time of development that we do not have time to fully understand what is happening in time and time. Currently, there is no unspoken thought or uncreated idea in any field. The effective use of modern media in the education of students is an important requirement of the present time. The Internet, which has become an information space, is especially important in this regard. Therefore, it is necessary to improve knowledge and skills in the field of media.

Keywords: *mass media, information, internet, internet network, media education, media education, methods, creative thinking.*

Relevance of the topic. President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: ".. as we aim to make Uzbekistan a developed country, we can achieve this only through rapid reforms, science and innovation. For this, first of all, it is necessary to educate the new generation of personnel who will be proactive reformers, who will think strategically, and who will be educated and qualified. That's why we started reforming all stages of education, from kindergarten to higher education. In order to increase the knowledge and level of not only young people, but also members of our society as a whole, first

of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed. Where there is no knowledge, there will be backwardness, ignorance and, of course, going astray." - their opinions confirm how important scientific development is for the future of our country.

We live in such a time of development that we do not have time to fully understand what is happening in time and time. Currently, there is no unspoken thought or uncreated idea in any field. All you have to do is access the Internet to get information on the topic you want. However, human spirituality and creativity cannot be compared with anything.

The effective use of modern media in the education of students is an important requirement of the present time. The Internet, which has become an information space, is especially important in this regard.

Nowadays, the development of information technologies, their becoming a part of our daily life, demands that we pay attention to this field not only in social life, but also in the field of education. The use of pedagogical technologies during the lesson has a positive effect on the quality of children's learning.

Opinions about the nature and characteristics of media education have become the most discussed issue in the pedagogical environment in recent years. Professor A.V. Fedorov media education for the purpose of training creative, communicative potentials, critical thinking, full perception, interpretation, analysis and evaluation of media texts and various forms of self-expression using media technology to form a culture of communication with mass media. sees it as a process of personal development with the help of mass communication (media) tools and materials. He rightly emphasizes that the active use of television, radio, video, cinematography, press, Internet, mass media helps a person to better understand the language of media culture. So, media education is designed to prepare people for life in an information society. Media education should occupy a worthy place in the education sector of our country, including in the public education system. In fulfilling this task, it is important to improve the activities of pedagogues' retraining and professional development institutions in the public education system, to increase the quality of education. - pedagogical research is not being conducted either.

Tasks of the research: Elucidate the content of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods; Improving the mechanisms of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods; Clarify the pedagogical possibilities of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods; Improving the technology of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods.

Scientific news of the study:

- The content, essence, and importance of the topic of the mechanisms of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods will be highlighted.

- Mechanisms, methods, directions, instructions for teaching students to think creatively through media education methods are developed.

- Criteria will be developed and tools will be selected to further increase the efficiency of the mechanisms of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods.

- A continuous system of mechanisms for teaching students to think creatively through media education methods will be developed and put into practice.

Practical results of the study: Methodological recommendations on improving the modular technology of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods have been developed;

The criteria and indicators of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods have been clarified;

The electronic system of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods has been improved;

A model of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods was developed and implemented in educational practice.

Theoretical and practical significance of research results: The theoretical significance of the research is that it is enriched with theoretical approaches to the development of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods; The criteria and indicators for determining the level of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods, as well as the development of scientific

and methodical recommendations that provide a positive solution to the research problem, the norms of teaching students to think creatively through media education methods have been developed. is explained by the fact that it has been improved.

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